

A CRITICAL EVALUATION OF THROUGH-THICKNESS TEST METHODS

William R. Broughton

*Composites and Polymers Properties Branch
Centre for Materials Measurement and Technology, National Physical Laboratory
Queens Road, Teddington, Middlesex, TW11 0LW, United Kingdom*

SUMMARY: This paper critically evaluates a number of through-thickness test methods in terms of key factors relating to fibre format or architecture, matrix type, load introduction, specimen preparation and the potential for standardisation. Consideration is given to both the practicality of using a test method in an industrial environment, in terms of ensuring "fitness for purpose" and to the degree of uniformity of stress distributions throughout the test geometry. The evaluation is based on a comprehensive database obtained from tests conducted on a range fibre-reinforced plastic composites, including continuous and discontinuous, aligned, random and woven fabric fibre formats in thermoset and thermoplastic matrices. In order to meet the challenge, a number of new test geometries have been developed and experimentally evaluated.

KEYWORDS: polymer composites, through-thickness, test methods, tension, compression, elastic constants, strength, failure modes.

INTRODUCTION

An increasing demand for intrinsic through-thickness (T-T) strength and stiffness properties for use as input data for design and analysis of polymer matrix composite (PMC) structures has stimulated the development of T-T test methods. T-T tensile, compressive and shear properties are frequently required for both "thick" section applications and for "thin" sections where there is a concern that two-dimensional analysis is inadequate. There is a tendency to associate interlaminar stresses with "thick" sections, however, interlaminar stresses and strains may be induced in "thin" laminates through the application of membrane (ie in-plane) loads. In an attempt to generate this data, it has become apparent that methods applicable to conventional metallic materials are not suitable for testing PMCs. The unique and diverse nature of PMCs, introduces additional problems relating to anisotropy, low T-T tensile and shear properties, coupling effects and the relative difficulties of producing laminates of adequate thickness. These problems have provided a major challenge to researchers in finding solutions in order to generate reliable engineering data.

This paper critically evaluates a number of test methods for measuring T-T properties under tensile, compressive and shear loads. Each method is examined in terms of the level of standardisation, elastic and strength properties obtained, material suitability, material thickness requirements, specimen fabrication, test apparatus, methods of data measurement and data reduction procedures. The evaluation is based on a comprehensive database obtained from tests conducted on a range PMCs, including continuous and discontinuous, aligned, random and

woven fabric fibre formats in thermoset and thermoplastic matrices. In order to meet the challenge a number of new test geometries have been developed and experimentally evaluated.

The experimental results clearly demonstrate that many of the mechanical test methods evaluated produce reliable engineering data required for quality assessment and design. A number of these test methods are suitable for development into ISO standards. The paper contains recommendations and guidance as to the use of the remaining test methods.

THROUGH-THICKNESS TENSION AND COMPRESSION

This section provides a brief description of three directly loaded configurations that can be used to evaluate T-T tension and/or compression properties of PMCs:

- Rectangular (unwaisted) block
- Short waisted rectangular block with a plain radius gauge-section
- I-section

Waisted (Fig. 1) and unwaisted rectangular (ie parallel-sided) specimens can be loaded in either tension or compression, along the T-T axis. In tension, the load is introduced via reusable stainless steel or aluminium loading bars, adhesively bonded to the specimen. Compressive load is applied by placing the specimen between two hardened steel parallel platens with the specimen located at the centre of the platens in closely fitting recesses. A four pillar die set is often used to ensure uniform loading to the ends of the specimen. Commercial units are available at a reasonable price. The two geometries are complementary, with waisted and parallel-sided blocks providing strength and elastic property data, respectively.

Fig. 1: Waisted block specimens: (left) plain radius; and (right) DERA.

Bonding loading bars to fibre-reinforced thermoplastics (eg glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene) is an extremely difficult task. Commercial grade adhesives proved ineffective. Although, surface treatments, such as corona discharge and flame treatment may enhance adhesion, these techniques require expensive equipment, an economic option unavailable to most mechanical test laboratories. An alternative approach, developed at the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), uses an I-section, where the load is applied to the specimen via the top and bottom flanges by two sets of hardened stainless steel stirrups (Fig. 2). The I-section is only suitable for measuring T-T tensile strengths.

Fig. 2: I-section tensile specimen

Tables 1 and 2 compare T-T tensile and compressive data obtained from a diverse range of PMCs that have been tested by the three methods. Note that default values given in Tables 1 and 2 are bracketed (ie elastic properties assumed to be symmetric in the X-Z and Y-Z planes). Elastic and strength property measurements were in reasonable agreement with corresponding data [1] obtained from tests carried out by the Defence Evaluation Research Agency (DERA), using a waisted block specimen, developed at Fort Halstead. The DERA waisted block specimen (Fig. 1), which has a nominal T-T dimension of 38 mm, can be used to measure T-T elastic and strength properties in both tension and compression.

Rectangular Block

Square cross-section specimens, 15 mm square, with T-T dimensions (ie thickness) ranging from 18 to 40 mm were machined from a range of PMCs (see Tables 1 and 2). This test geometry provides consistent and reliable elastic property data for both monolithic and layered (ie sandwich constructions) materials, and is amenable to standardisation for this purpose. The test geometry is unsuitable for generating strength data. According to stress analysis [2], a length-to-width ratio of 2:1 should be sufficient to guarantee a relatively uniform stress state at the specimen mid-section (ie negligible end-effects), and prevent the possibility of buckling when loaded in compression. Elastic properties were approximately the same; independent of laminate thickness, test method or loading mode. The coefficient of variation (CV) for E_{zz} was generally less than 5.

Table 1: Through-thickness tensile measurements

Test Method	E_{zz} (GPa)	ν_{zx}	ν_{zy}	S_{zz} (MPa)
<u>Aligned carbon-fibre/epoxy</u>				
Rectangular Block (40 mm)	9.9 ± 0.1	$0.019 \pm .002$	0.55 ± 0.01	N/A
Rectangular Block (20 mm)	9.9 ± 0.4	0.020 ± 0.002	0.51 ± 0.01	N/A
Plain Waisted Block (40 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	78 ± 7
DERA Waisted Block (38 mm)*	9.5 ± 0.1	0.020 ± 0.001	0.47 ± 0.01	71 ± 6
<u>2/2 twill glass-fibre fabric/epoxy</u>				
Rectangular Block (40 mm)	11.0 ± 0.4	0.19 ± 0.01	[0.19 ± 0.01]	N/A
DERA Waisted Block (38 mm)*	10.7 ± 0.3	0.18 ± 0.04	0.17 ± 0.01	36 ± 1
<u>Discontinuous glass-fibre/nylon 66</u>				
Rectangular Block (20 mm)	4.4 ± 0.1	0.27 ± 0.04	0.41 ± 0.02	N/A
I-section (20 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	69 ± 7
<u>Random glass-fibre mat/polypropylene</u>				
Rectangular Block (18 mm)	3.5 ± 0.1	0.16 ± 0.04	0.18	N/A
I-section (18 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	5.7 ± 1.6

Table 2: Through-thickness compression measurements

Test Method	E_{zz} (GPa)	ν_{zx}	ν_{zy}	S_{zz} (MPa)
<u>Aligned carbon-fibre/epoxy</u>				
Rectangular Block (40 mm)	10.0 ± 0.1	0.022 ± 0.001	0.52 ± 0.01	263 ± 3
Rectangular Block (20 mm)	9.9 ± 0.1	0.020 ± 0.001	0.56 ± 0.01	256 ± 6
Sandwich Block (40 mm)	10.0	0.02	0.52	258 ± 3
Plain Waisted Block (40 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	343 ± 7
Plain Waisted Block (20 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	344 ± 10
DERA Waisted Block (38 mm)*	10.3 ± 0.2	0.020 ± 0.005	0.47 ± 0.01	297 ± 5
<u>2/2 twill glass-fibre fabric/epoxy</u>				
Rectangular Block (40 mm)	12.4	0.21	0.21	588 ± 25
Plain Waisted Block	N/A	N/A	N/A	543 ± 5
DERA Waisted Block (38 mm)*	11.8 ± 0.2	0.19 ± 0.01	0.18 ± 0.01	545 ± 6
<u>Discontinuous glass-fibre/nylon 66</u>				
Rectangular Block (20 mm)	4.3	0.21	0.44	190 ± 8
Plain Waisted Block (20 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	195 ± 5
<u>Random glass-fibre mat/polypropylene</u>				
Rectangular Block (18 mm)	4.2	0.21	[0.21]	181 ± 14
Plain Waisted Block (18 mm)	N/A	N/A	N/A	210 ± 9

() denotes T-T dimension

* Data from Ref. 1.

A rectangular block is a relatively straightforward and economic specimen to test, requiring no special loading fixture. Although not essential, the use of a high precision die set will ensure

uniform axial compressive loading. Specimen fabrication is uncomplicated and economical. Caution needs to be exercised to ensure that misalignment, at both the fabrication and testing stages is minimised. Small misalignments will induce bending, resulting in differential strains on opposing faces of the specimen. Specimens were machined to the required profile by wet grinding.

Tensile specimens were adhesively bonded to the loading bars using a high strength, two part epoxy adhesive. For good alignment, it was essential that all faces were flat and parallel with the opposite surface, and perpendicular with adjacent surfaces. A room temperature curing adhesive was used to avoid residual stresses at the adherend interface. During the curing process, specimens were held in a gluing fixture to ensure accurate alignment between the loading blocks and the loading axis.

A major disadvantage is in the number of strain gauges (4 biaxial rosettes) required for the highest accuracy measurement of axial and transverse strain. A biaxial strain gauge with an active length of 2 mm was bonded on each face of the specimen at the mid-section, with gauges aligned parallel to and perpendicular to the loading direction. Strain averaging was used to account for possible bending strains. Strain gauge numbers could possibly be reduced if there was sufficient confidence in the quality and alignment of the specimen. Axial and transverse extensometers can also be used to measure the T-T elastic properties of 40 mm thick material loaded in tension (eg 2/2 twill fabric shown in Table 1). Extensometers are not particularly suitable for use with thin tensile specimens or compression specimens. Data reduction is straightforward with the applied stress, σ , given by:

$$\sigma = \frac{P}{A} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied force and A is the specimen cross-sectional area.

As expected, rectangular tensile specimens failed consistently at the adhesive joints between the specimen and the metallic loading bars for all but the weakest materials, thus invalidating the strength data obtained. Strength values obtained from compression tests were consistent to within $\pm 10\%$, and in reasonable agreement with the strength data obtained using the waisted block geometries. In compression, failure invariably initiates at the specimen ends, independent of material anisotropy and degree of homogeneity. The presence of stress concentrations in these regions causes premature failure, hence the lower strength value. This method is relatively insensitive to material flaws (eg porosity). A major problem with measuring T-T properties of relatively thin laminates (ie 10 mm thick) was surmounted, by adhesively bonding three layers of material together, to form a sandwich construction. A high strength, two part epoxy adhesive was used to bond the layers together. Compression data obtained from tests on aligned carbon-fibre/epoxy, demonstrated the effectiveness of this approach.

Waisted Block (Plain Radius)

As previously mentioned, short rectangular columns of uniform cross-section are unsuitable for generating T-T strength data, as failure invariably occurs at the specimen ends. An alternative approach, is to use waisted specimens with either a circular or elliptical profile extending along

the entire gauge-length of the specimen [2-4]. The reduction in cross-sectional area, promotes failure at the specimen mid-thickness. This relatively straightforward approach can be used to measure both T-T tensile and compressive strengths of monolithic and sandwich constructions. Compared to rectangular blocks, specimen fabrication is expensive and labour intensive.

A waisted specimen with a plain radius along the entire gauge-length has been developed at the NPL (Fig. 1). This specimen has a nominal thickness of 40 mm, a fillet radius of 30 mm and 25 mm square ends. The gauge-section is 32 mm long, with a cross-section approximately 16 mm square at the specimen mid-thickness. The large fillet radius (ie 30 mm) reduces the stress concentration in the vicinity of the fillet root, although the stress state within the gauge-length is less uniform than an equivalent sized rectangular prism. This test geometry may be scaled down by a factor of 2, with minimal effect on compressive strength (Table 2). End effects increase slightly with a reduction of thickness (ie height).

Fig. 3: Plain waisted block specimen

Specimen preparation, bonding procedure, loading configuration and test conditions are similar to those employed for rectangular block specimens. Alignment is critical for low-failure strain systems, as bending stresses produced through eccentric loading can result in premature failure. The applied stress, σ , is determined using Equation (1), where A in this case is the mid-thickness cross-sectional area of the specimen.

T-T tensile failure occurred in a plane orthogonal to the loading direction at the specimen mid-thickness. Shear is the predominant cause of failure in all fibre-reinforced plastic composites tested in compression; independent of the material microstructure. Failure is often instantaneous and catastrophic resulting in diagonal and interlaminar cracking, with failure modes generally remaining unaffected by a reduction in specimen size. For woven fabrics, two orthogonal fracture plains can be observed at 45° to the T-T axis (Fig. 4).

Provided the adhesive joints have superior strength and fatigue performance than the composite material, waisted tensile specimens could be used under cyclic loading conditions. Environmental testing could also be performed with the same provision that the adhesive joints can withstand the environmental conditions. In compression, this test geometry is compatible

with both cyclic and environmental testing. The presence of frictional forces at the loading faces will probably result in fretting.

Fig. 4: Failed: (left) DERA; (centre) plain radius; and (right) rectangular blocks

I-Section

The test is simple and economic, and there are no major problems associated with alignment or adhesive bonding (Fig. 2). A special loading fixture is required (ie stirrups), however, the overall costs involved are relatively low compared with bonded configurations. Tests have been successfully conducted on glass-fibre reinforced nylon 66 and glass-fibre reinforced polypropylene. The load is applied to the specimen via the top and bottom flanges by two sets of stirrups, with the inside surfaces of the flanges resting directly on the stirrups.

Specimens have a nominal T-T dimension of 20 mm and a uniform thickness of 5 mm. The flange width and thickness are 20 mm and 5 mm, respectively. The 10 mm gauge-length has a plain waisted width. The radius of curvature of the gauge-length is 5 mm. The cross-section is 5 mm square at the specimen mid-thickness. Ideally, the fillet radius should be larger to minimise the high stresses and stress gradients in this region, however this is not a practicable option for thin laminates. The flange thickness was sufficient to ensure failure occurred within the gauge-length.

Table 3: Tensile and compression test methods suitable for standardisation

Method	Elastic Properties	Strengths
<u>Tension</u> Rectangular Block Plain Waisted Block I-Section	Suitable. Not applicable. Not applicable.	Not suitable. Suitable -thermoset systems only. Suitable - needs further development.
<u>Compression</u> Rectangular Block Plain Waisted Block	Recommend. Not applicable.	QA only Suitable.

THROUGH-THICKNESS SHEAR

The number of test methods that can be used for T-T shear characterisation is limited, with all techniques demonstrating deficiencies. This section evaluates two methods that have been widely adopted for characterising T-T shear properties of PMCs, the double-notch and V-notched beam (Iosipescu) test methods. The V-notched beam method (ASTM D 5379 [5]) can provide in-plane and T-T shear moduli for all isotropic and anisotropic materials, and in many cases the shear strength. The double-notch method, which consists of loading a non-symmetrically notched coupon in uniaxial tension or compression is used to measure interlaminar shear strength. This method is available as ASTM D 3846 [6], and is quoted as an appendix to BS 4994 [7] and BS 6464 [8]. ASTM D 3846 specifies compressive loading, and the two BSI standards tensile loading. Typical T-T shear data obtained using these methods is shown in Table 4. Default values are bracketed (ie assumed material symmetry in the X-Z and Y-Z planes). Tests were conducted according ASTM specifications. Shear strengths obtained using the two test geometries were generally in good agreement [9].

Table 4: Through-thickness shear measurements (* = non-shear failure)

Test Method	G_{xz} (GPa)	G_{yz} (GPa)	S_{xz} (MPa)	S_{yz} (MPa)
<u>Aligned carbon-fibre/epoxy</u>				
V-Notched Beam	5.30 ± 0.31	2.93 ± 0.25	111 ± 2	$64 \pm 9^*$
V-Notched Beam (sandwich)	5.37	3.18	105	52*
Double-Notch	N/A	N/A	75 ± 12	N/A
<u>2/2 twill glass-fibre fabric/epoxy</u>				
V-Notched Beam	4.12 ± 0.14	$[4.12 \pm 0.14]$	68.4 ± 0.9	$[68.4 \pm 0.9]$
Double-Notch	N/A	N/A	64.9 ± 1.8	$[64.9 \pm 1.8]$
<u>Discontinuous glass-fibre/nylon 66</u>				
V-Notched Beam	1.68 ± 0.06	-	$56.9 \pm 3.6^*$	$58.4 \pm 4.8^*$
Double-Notch	N/A	N/A	66.4 ± 4.8	$[66.4 \pm 4.8]$
<u>Random glass-fibre mat/polypropylene</u>				
V-Notched Beam	1.04 ± 0.04	$[1.04 \pm 0.04]$	22.7 ± 0.8	$[22.7 \pm 0.8]$
Double-Notch	N/A	N/A	18.1 ± 3.3	$[18.1 \pm 3.3]$

Double-Notch

Due to their simplicity, test geometries incorporating a double-notch have been widely employed in the measurement of interlaminar shear strength. The most reliable approach is to load a double-notch specimen in compression, with the specimen supported along its entire length to minimise out-of-plane deformation, as specified in ASTM D 3846 (Fig. 5). Tests were conducted using specimens 79.5 mm long and 10.0 mm wide (NB. ASTM D 3846 recommends 12.7 mm). Two parallel notches, one on each opposite face of the specimen and 6.4 mm (0.25 in) apart, were cut across the entire width of the specimen and centrally located along its length. The notch width was ± 1.5 mm and extended to the specimen mid-plane.

Linear-elastic stress analysis has shown that the shear stress distribution along the mid-plane between the notches is non-uniform with high shear stresses in the vicinity of the notches. Non-linear finite element analysis, conducted at the NPL, has indicated that the stress concentration at the notches is close to unity for an isotropic specimen loaded according to ASTM 3846. Data reduction is simple, with the applied stress determined using Equation (1), where A is the cross-sectional area between the notches.

The method specified in ASTM 3846 is relatively straightforward to perform, requiring a support fixture of moderate cost. This loading configuration provides consistent strength data with interlaminar failure regularly occurring along the mid-plane joining the two notches. T-T shear strength data is generally consistent with results obtained using the V-notched beam method, implying the shear stress concentration at the notches is close to unity (Table 3). Specimen preparation and testing is relatively straightforward, although the quality of machining the notches has a significant effect on strength data. Notch depth must be accurately machined to the required depth of half the specimen thickness (ie mid-plane). Fractographic examination of the failure surfaces reveals shear dominated mixed-mode failure. This method is particularly suited to testing thin laminates (ie 2.5 to 10 mm thick).

Fig. 5: Double-notch and V-notched beam tests

V-Notched Beam Shear

This test employs a double edge-notched, flat, rectangular specimen. Tests were carried out on monolithic materials, and a three-layered sandwich construction, according to ASTM D 5379 using the loading configuration shown in Fig. 5. Specimens were 76 mm in length, 20 mm wide (ie T-T dimension) and 5 mm thick (nominal). Two 90° angle notches with a notch root radius of 1.3 mm were machined at the edge mid-length with faces oriented at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the longitudinal axis, to a depth of 20% of the specimen width (ie 4 mm). Shear strain was measured by bonding two biaxial strain gauges, one on each opposite face of the specimen at its centre in the area

between the notches. The strain gauges had an active gauge-length of 1 mm and were aligned at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the longitudinal axis of the specimen. Applied stress is determined from Equation (1), where A is the cross-sectional area between the notches.

Providing adequate material thickness is available (ie 10 mm), this method can be used to measure in-plane and T-T shear modulus and shear strength (Table 3) for a diverse range of composite materials. Differences between shear moduli, due to out-of-plane deformation, can be as high as 10% for a batch of nominally identical specimens. To ensure maximum accuracy, shear modulus is determined from the average response of back-to-back biaxial rosettes. At present the standard requires only one specimen from a batch to be tested in this manner provided the amount of twist for this test piece is no greater than 3%.

Table 5: Shear test methods suitable for standardisation

Method	Elastic Properties	Strengths
Double-Notch V-Notched Beam	Not applicable. Strongly recommend.	Strongly recommend. Strongly recommend - caution on failure mode.

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